

Adsorption Voltammetry Determination of Lysine Traces of its *o*-Chlorobenzaldehyde Derivative

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An adsorption voltammetric method for the determination of lysine is reported, based on the reduction of the Schiff base compound formed by lysine and *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde in phosphate buffer solution (pH 11.1). The Schiff base product can be adsorbed on a hanging mercury drop electrode and reduced with peak potential of about -1.15 V (vs SCE). The derivative peak height is linearly proportional to the concentration of lysine in the range 1.0×10^{-8} – 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, and the detection limit is 5.0×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³. The method has been applied for the determination of trace lysine in some food samples without any pre-separation step with satisfactory results.

The determination of amino acid is very important in the study of the life sciences. In general, the identification and determination of amino acids can be done by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GS-MS) and amino acid analyzer^{1,2}, however, the methods are expensive and laborious. Spectrophotometric methods based on the formation of coloured compound suffer from poor sensitivity and selectivity³. Electrochemical methods have also been used to determine amino acids. Fonseca and Arredondo⁴ studied the nickel(II) catalytic pre-waves yielded by some amino acids in borate medium and a d.c. polarographic method for the determination has been proposed in the concentration range from 1.0×10^{-5} to 8.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³. Moreira and Fogg⁵ determined histidine by differential-pulse adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry of its Cu complex, and the method permits the limit down to 5×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³.

In this work, the adsorption voltammetry of electro-inactive lysine has been studied based on the formation of the Schiff base compound formed by lysine and *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde. The derivatization product can be adsorbed on a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) and reduced at a peak potential of about -1.15 V (vs SCE). The procedure may be directly applied to the determination of lysine in food and nutrition samples.

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions for electrochemical analysis :

Selection of electrolyte solution : Borax-NaOH, acetate, carbonate and phosphate-NaOH buffer media were tested. The results show that only in phosphate-NaOH medium, a well-defined voltammetric peak is obtained. So phosphate-NaOH was chosen as electrolyte at an optimum concentration of 0.15 mol dm⁻³.

Effect of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde concentration on the peak current : At constant lysine concentrations, the peak current of the lysine derivative increased with the increase of the concentration of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, then becoming stable. The optimum concentration range was found to be 2.5×10^{-3} – 4.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, hence 3.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ concentration was selected.

Effect of pH on i_p and E_p : The effect of pH on the height of the peak was studied (Fig. 1). The largest peak current was obtained at pH 10.9–11.2, hence pH 11.1 was chosen as the optimum for quantitative determination. The negative shift of E_p values with increasing pH values and the slope of the E_p vs pH plot (0.060 V/pH) indicated the involvement of proton transfer preceding the potential-determining step⁶.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the peak current and peak potential; 0.15 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer solution (pH 11.10), 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 6.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ of lysine, $t_a = 60$ s, $v = 100$ mV s⁻¹.

Relationship between peak current and the time of derivative reaction : Peak current increased with increasing reaction time till the reaction equilibrium was set up at 20 min. Thus, 20 min was chosen as the derivative reaction time.

Adsorptive and voltammetric characteristic of lysine :

Effect of pre-concentration time and scan rate : The increase of peak current with pre-concentration time indicated that the derivative can be adsorbed on the surface of the electrode. When the t_a gets a certain value, the peak current does not increase any longer (Fig. 2) and this condition means that equilibrium is set up. The experimental results show that the reduction peak current of the lysine derivative is linearly related to the scan rate, $\log i_p/\log v = 0.96$, indicating that the reduction wave is an adsorption wave⁷.

Fig. 2. Effect of pre-concentration time on i_p ; 0.15 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer solution (pH 11.10), 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 6.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ of lysine, $v = 100$ mV s⁻¹.

Cyclic voltammetry : Typical cyclic voltammetric characteristic of the derivative of lysine is shown in Fig. 3. A cathodic wave appears at -1.15 V (vs SCE) and no corresponding anodic wave appears in the potential range -0.9 to -1.3 V. This implies that the electrochemical reduction process is totally irreversible. The negative shift of E_p with increasing the scan rate also indicated it. The apparent transfer coefficient (α_n) can be taken from the peak half-width ($W_{1/2}$) according to the equation, $\alpha_n = 62.5/W_{1/2}$. The average peak half-width at different scan rates and different concentrations of lysine is 56 mV. From this value, α_n value of $\alpha = 0.56$ and n value of 2 can be obtained. So the electrode process of the reduction of the derivative is a 2e process.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of lysine derivative; 0.15 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer solution (pH 11.10), 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ of lysine, $t_a = 60$ s, $v = 100$ mV s⁻¹.

Analytical application : A 300-fold excess of tryptophan, tyrosine, histidine, aspartic acid and phenylalanine interfere with the determination of 6.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ lysine. Two reduction peaks of cysteine were observed at -0.6 and -0.8 V respectively, but as these were at more positive potentials than that of the lysine derivative, they did not interfere. Under the optimum experimental condition, a linear relationship holds between the derivative peak current of the reduction of the lysine derivative and the concentration of lysine in the range 1.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³. The detection limit is 5.0×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³.

A certain amount of sample solution was added into the cell, then determined as the above experimental method. The result obtained by two successive standard additions for samples are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF SAMPLE ANALYZED*

Sample	Content of lysine determined	Deviation coefficient	Recovery %
Apollo oral solution**	133.2 mg/L	2.96%	97
Condiment of fast food	1.17 mg/g	3.04%	101

*Average value of 5 determination. **Nutrition

Experimental

A 79-1 voltammetric analyser (Jinan Electronic Instrument Factory, China) coupled with a 3086-11 X-Y recorder (Shanghai Dahua Instrument Factory, China) was used in connection with a self-made cell. A three-electrode system consisted of a HMDE (SH-84) as the working electrode, a

Pt plate as the counter electrode and a SCE as the reference electrode. All potentials were measured against the SCE. The pH values were measured with a pHs-2 pH meter (Shanghai Second Analytical Instrument Factory, China).

A stock solution (1×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³) of lysine was prepared in water and kept in a refrigerator. A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde was prepared in 25% ethanol. Solutions of 0.25 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer (pH 11.2) and 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaOH were used. All chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as such. Triple-distilled water from a quartz still was used in all experiments.

Procedure : An aliquot of lysine solution, phosphate-NaOH buffer solution (18 ml) and *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde solution (0.9 ml) were transferred into the cell and diluted to 30 ml with water. The solution was deaerated for about 20 min with nitrogen. The measurements were carried out after a pre-concentration step in which the solution was

stirred for 60 s and a pre-concentration potential E_a of -0.90 V was applied. After a rest period of 15 s, the voltammetric curve was recorded from -0.90 to -1.30 V and the first derivative peak current measured at a potential of about -1.15 V.

References

1. A. K. SINGH and M. A. ASHREF, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1989, **69**, 245.
2. A. MURAI, Y. TAKEUCHI and K. HIRAYAMA, *Shitsuryo Bunseki*, 1987, **35**, 343.
3. P. J. LAMOTHE and P. G. MCCORMICK, *Anal. Chem.*, 1973, **45**, 1906; K. NONDA, J. SEKINO and K. IMAI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1983, **55**, 940.
4. J. M. L. FONSECA and M. C. ARREDONDO, *Analyst*, 1982, **107**, 903.
5. J. C. MOREIRA and A. G. FOGG, *Analyst*, 1990, **115**, 41.
6. P. ZUMAN and L. MEITES, *Prog. Polarogr.*, 1972, **3**, 85.
7. E. LAVIRON, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1974, **52**, 355.